

Organizational Ripple Effects:
A Scoping Review Protocol of Managerially Driven Spillovers

Protocol Information

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Anticipated Start Date: April 2023

Anticipated Completion Date: August 2024

Abstract

Background: Spillover effects reflect the unintended impact of actions, decisions, and behaviour. Although these phenomena have received broad scholarly attention due to their frequency and wide-ranging consequences on individuals, teams, and organizations, spillover effects remain an ill-defined concept, and the literature is fragmented across various management disciplines. This scoping review aims to demystify the landscape of managerially driven spillover effects on the emotions, behaviours, knowledge, cognition, or performance of intraorganizational stakeholders.

Methods: The scoping review study described in the protocol examines peer-reviewed articles and grey literature from multiple sources according to the methodology suggested by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Our search sources for peer-reviewed articles will include the EBSCO Business Source Ultimate, Web of Science, Scopus, and INFORMS PubsOnline databases. Additionally, we will examine the grey literature on intraorganizational spillovers, from sources such as the EBSCO Open Dissertations database. We will export references to Rayyan and two independent reviewers will screen articles to create the pool of articles for the systematic review. Additionally, we will employ the Mixed Method Appraisal Tool to evaluate the included articles' quality.

Discussion: Our study aims to provide definitional clarity on spillover effects, map the the origins, dimensions, and impact of managerially initiated spillover effects on intraorganizational stakeholders. Furthermore, this review will address gaps in the relevant literature and identify themes for future research.

Scoping Review Registration: OSF (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/GSRWX>), Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13598063>)

Keywords: Spillover Effect, Contagion, Intraorganizational Behaviour, Managers, Executives, Cognition, Behaviour, Affect, Performance

Overview

The existing literature on organizational behaviour has extensively studied the affective dimensions of spillovers with a particular emphasis on the impact of emotional contagion on job and organizational outcomes (Barsade, 2002; Vijayalakshmi and Bhattacharyya, 2012; Tee, 2015; Barsade et al., 2018; Banerjee and Srivastava, 2019). In their conceptual model Barsade et al. (2018) indicated that individual (e.g., dedication to team, demographics, extroversion) and structural factors (e.g., type of industry, task interdependence) moderate the initiation of emotional contagion inside organizations and that emotional contagion phenomena relate to various attitudes (e.g., organizational commitment, job satisfaction) as well as to performance measures (e.g., intragroup cooperation, job performance). In addition, certain studies of spillovers underline the technological (e.g., production output) and social/behavioural (e.g., team performance) dimensions of spillovers (Martinez-Carrasco, 2017), while a recent review paper by Shi et al. (2022) synthesizes the types of events that can trigger spillovers between organizations (inter-organizational spillovers). Types of spillovers encountered in organizational life include knowledge and innovation spillovers as outlined by Aghion and Jaravel (2015) in relation to the R&D function of firms, industry-wide corporate reputation spillovers (Barnett and Hoffman, 2008), “peer effects” that foster entrepreneurship (Field et al., 2016) and “transfer effects” from previous acquisitions that can impact the performance of future ones.

However, we note possible definitional overlaps in the broader context of social sciences, since spillover phenomena have been described with various terms such as “social contagion” (Levy, 1992), “financial contagion” (Allen and Gale, 2000), “emotional contagion”, (Barsade, 2002), “transfer effects” (Finkelstein and Halebian, J., 2002), “behavioural contagion” (Cheng, 2014), “ripple effect” (Marques, 2006), “peer effects” (Field et al., 2016) and “peer response” (Chan et al., 2021). Furthermore, the dimensions of spillovers inside

organizations, which encompass not just affective aspects but also structural and technological ones, are not yet completely understood. Consequently, these topics warrant further research.

Study Objectives – Study Rationale

This study aims to provide a comprehensive review of spillovers in the context of management and organizational behaviour. We will examine the overlaps in definitions and in the dimensions of intraorganizational spillover events aiming to provide conceptual clarity. Our review will explore spillovers across three levels: micro-level spillovers (i.e., intrapersonal or interpersonal spillovers), mezzo-level spillovers (i.e., intragroup spillovers), and macro-level spillovers (i.e., intergroup spillovers). In defining spillovers, we will consider whether the relevant literature emphasizes the positive or negative aspects of these phenomena. In addition, an objective of the review is to reduce the disparity between the affective dimensions of spillover phenomena and the technological ones (e.g., output spillovers), which are frequently overlooked. The review will also investigate the causes of spillovers, determining whether they are driven by specific events or by general moods and attitudes. Furthermore, the study will review the factors that moderate spillover effects. Finally, we intend to present the outcomes of spillover phenomena, including their effects on the behaviour, emotions, and knowledge of several stakeholders inside the organization.

Methodology

For the workflow of our study, we will adhere to the methodology suggested by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). Regarding study selection we will employ the PRISMA extension (Figure 1) for scoping reviews (Tricco et al., 2018).

Figure 1. The PRISMA-ScR flowchart for our review.

1. Identifying the Research Questions

We can summarize our research questions as follows.

Research Questions

- What are the definitions and potential conceptual overlaps among “spillovers”, “linkages”, “contagion”, “peer effect”, “transfer effect”, and “ripple effect” in the management/organizational behavior literature?
- What are the types of managerially-driven spillover phenomena?
- What are the managerial-related events or general moods and attitudes that may lead to spillover effects?
- What are the theories that have been proposed to explain managerially-driven spillover phenomena?
- What research methods have been used to investigate managerially-driven spillover phenomena?
- What are the key challenges or gaps in the current understanding of managerially-driven spillover phenomena that need to be addressed by future research?

2. Identifying Relevant Studies

Inclusion Criteria - Search Framework – Search Strategy

Figure 2 illustrates the PCC (people, concept, context) protocol, as proposed by Peters et al. (2017), that we will use to identify eligible studies for our review.

People

This study focuses on managers at all levels of the corporate hierarchy. We are interested in studies in which managers are affected, directly or indirectly, because of their role (i.e., CEO dismissal) or their actions (i.e., an investment decision). Managers are employees within an

organization whose responsibilities include planning and coordinating organizational activities, communicating and delegating tasks, leading and supervising others, and regulating the use of resources to achieve organizational objectives. The review would include top level managers (e.g., CEOs, CFOs, CTOs, CMOs), mid-level managers (e.g., department heads), and first-line managers (e.g., those collaborating directly with employees involved in the production of goods and the provision of services).

Concept

This review will examine the phenomenon of spillovers, which are typically unintended outcomes and have been referred to using various terms such as “contagion”, “externalities”, “transfer effects”, “ripple effects”, “peer effects”, and “peer response”.

Context

Our review will include studies that mention spillover effects related to human behaviour, cognition, emotion, mood, affect, attitude, knowledge, or performance in their full text. In addition, the full text of studies must make mention of “businesses” or “corporations” or “organizations” or “firms”. The articles included in the review may examine spillover phenomena that relate to individual, group, and organizational outcomes. The study will include all available sources as of the end of 2023, with no other time constraints. Moreover, we will not impose any geographical constraints but will only our review articles written in English.

Figure 2. The PCC framework for “Managerially Driven Spillover Effects: A Scoping Review Protocol”

Sources

We will conduct our search using the EBSCO Business Source Ultimate, Web of Science, Scopus, and INFORMS Pubs Online databases.

For examining the grey literature, we will use EBSCO OpenDissertations. In addition, we will post an announcement in online scholar forums (e.g., AOM OB Listserv) requesting book chapters, unpublished article drafts, and conference proceedings. Furthermore, we intend to conduct a hand search on related articles as they are suggested by our search sources (e.g., in the “you may also like” section of the search results screen of the Web of Science database) and in review papers and well-cited studies.

Sample Search Terms

EBSCO Host

For our search using EBSCO Host, and particularly the Business Source Ultimate database, we will employ the following search terms:

AB= (spillover* OR contag* OR “peer effect*” OR “transfer effect*” OR “ripple effect*” OR “peer response*” OR externalit*) AND

AB = (executive* OR manager* OR “team leader*” OR CEO* OR CFO* OR CMO* OR CTO*)

TX = (emot* OR behavi#r* OR cogniti* OR affect* OR mood OR attitud* OR perform* OR knowledge) AND

TX = (business* OR corporat* OR organi#ation* OR firm*)

Web of Science (WoS)

For our Search using the Clarivate Web of Science (WoS) database, we are going utilize the following search queries:

(spillover* OR contag* OR "peer effect*" OR "transfer effect*" OR "ripple effect*" OR "peer response*" OR externalit*)

(Topic)

AND (executive* OR manager* OR "team leader*" OR CEO* OR CFO* OR CMO* OR CTO*) (Topic)

AND (emot* OR "behavi*r*" OR cogniti* OR affect* OR mood OR attitud* OR perform* OR knowledge)

(All Fields)

AND (business* OR corporat* OR organi?ation* OR firm*)

(All Fields)

and English (Languages)

Scopus

For our Search in the Scopus database, we will use the following search queries:

(spillover* OR contag* OR "peer effect*" OR "transfer effect*" OR "ripple effect*" OR "follower effect*" OR "peer response*" OR externalit*)
(Title-Abstract-Keywords)

AND (executive* OR manager* OR "team leader*" OR CEO* OR CFO* OR CMO* OR CTO*)
(Title-Abstract-Keywords)

AND (emot* OR "behavi*r*" OR cogniti* OR affect* OR mood OR attitud* OR perform* OR knowledge)
(All Fields)

AND business* OR corporat* OR organi?ation* OR firm*)
(All Fields)

INFORMS PubsOnLine

For our Search using the INFORMS PubsOnLine database, which encompasses 17 academic journals, we are going to use the following search queries.

(spillover* OR contag* OR "peer effect*" OR "transfer effect*" OR "ripple effect*" OR "follower effect*" OR "peer response*" OR externalit*)
(Keywords)

AND (executive* OR manager* OR "team leader*" OR CEO* OR CFO* OR CMO* OR CTO*) (Keywords)

AND (emot* OR "behavi*r*" OR cogniti* OR affect* OR mood OR attitud* OR perform* OR knowledge)
(Anywhere)

AND (business* OR corporat* OR organi?ation* OR firm*)
(Anywhere)

Exclusion Criteria

We will exclude studies based on the following criteria:

- Studies that examine inter-organizational spillover phenomena
- Studies that do not identify managers as spillover focal points
- Studies that mention microeconomic externalities
- Studies referring to financial contagion

- Studies for which the full text is unavailable

3. Study Selection

We will evaluate abstracts to determine whether a study qualifies for inclusion. In case of doubt, we will review the full text. After removing duplicates, we will use the Rayyan software to manager references, screen and select articles. In Rayyan, two reviewers will evaluate abstracts independently and provide justifications for the exclusion of each publication. We will resolve any disagreements among the reviewers through discussion until no discrepancy is found.

4. Data Extraction

All data extracted from the remaining articles will be included in an Excel spreadsheet. For consistency purposes, an additional researcher will extract data from a number of studies (n=10). Then we will compare the results to those of the original reviewer. Should we spot any disagreements, we will modify the field of the Excel spreadsheet. After the completion of this process, the main researcher will begin extracting data from the remaining publications.

5. Collating, Summarizing, and Reporting Data

We will conduct a content and a thematic analysis. By summarizing the data, we aim to provide insights on the following issues:

- Definitions of intraorganizational spillovers
- Types of studies used to assess intraorganizational spillovers
- Sectors examined in studies of intraorganizational spillovers
- Events and activities related to intraorganizational spillovers
- Measure of impact of intraorganizational spillovers
- Antecedents and Outcomes of intraorganizational spillovers

- Themes for future research related to intraorganizational spillovers

We intend to report data using tables and diagrams. In addition, we aim to use the Mixed Method Appraisal Tool (MMAT; Hong et al., 2018) to assess the quality of the studies that will be included in our scoping review.

6. Consultation with stakeholders

After presenting our findings, we plan to consult management scholars and practitioners to amplify the theoretical and practical implications of our work. The consulting team will consist of four individuals from both industry and academia. This consultation process will serve to share our analysis with academics and managers, facilitate the explanation of our findings and gain valuable insights, comments, and suggestions. We will divide this process into two meetings; the first one to present the general objectives of our study and to discuss preliminary findings, and the second one to evaluate the entire body of our work as we near the completion of our review.

Discussion

Spillovers are multi-faceted occurrences that arise in organizations. They have an impact on various aspects of organizational life, including managerial decision-making, output, employee engagement, and organizational performance. The findings of this review will help us demystify the concept of intraorganizational spillover effects, map the domain, suggest ways to regulate spillover effects and identify areas for further research. Overall, we expect that our findings will be useful for scholars and professionals interested in comprehending and regulating spillover effects within organizations.

Amendments to Original Protocol

Please note that this amended version of the protocol has the following changes

1. Title

Original: "Managerially Initiated Spillover Effects: A Scoping Review Protocol"

Amended: "Organizational Ripple Effects: A Scoping Review Protocol of Managerially Driven Spillovers"

Reason: To emphasize the organizational context of spillover effects and highlight managers as focal points.

2. Dates of Inclusion

Original: Articles published up to December 31, 2022

Amended: Articles published up to December 31, 2023

Reason: A significant uptick in relevant literature was observed during the review composition.

3. Dates of Completion

Original: August 2023

Amended: August 2024

Reason: Search process, data extraction, and synthesis required more time than initially anticipated.

4. In-text citations

Minor amendments, relating to adding an in-text citation to Figure 1 and correcting in-text citation to Figure 2.

(These amendments were made on August 2nd, 2024.)

5. Updated abstract

Included dimensions relating to knowledge and performance in the protocol's abstract and made minor wording changes for clarity. Also, included Zenodo in the registries section and added the relevant DOI links.

6. Categorization of micro level spillovers

Original: "micro-level spillovers (i.e., intrapersonal spillovers), mezzo-level spillovers (i.e., interpersonal, or intragroup spillovers), and macro-level spillovers (i.e., intergroup spillovers)"

Amended: "micro-level spillovers (i.e., intrapersonal or interpersonal spillovers), mezzo-level spillovers (i.e., intragroup spillovers), and macro-level spillovers (i.e., intergroup spillovers)"

Reason: To better categorize interpersonal spillovers at the micro level.

(These amendments were made on August 30th, 2024.)

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